

Proposal

LISS panel grant 2023

Social class: an exploitation-based class scheme

1 Layperson summary

With this project we aim to enrich and innovate research in social stratification by collecting fine-grained data to operationalize an exploitation-based class scheme, currently underused in the social sciences. Current understanding of social inequality is based on indicators such as income and education, used as proxies for a person's social position and experiences. We argue that to really understand social inequality and stratification, we need better data on class dynamics between different socioeconomic positions in society and of people's understanding of their own position within the social hierarchy. Expanding the toolkit for understanding social stratification will enable researchers and policy makers to better analyse other problems related to inequality and polarization, such as voting behaviour and belief in meritocracy.

2 Background of the study and relationship to the literature

Recent years have seen a renewed interest in social class within the broader field of social inequality research, sparked by growing income inequality (Piketty, 2014) and popular publications on new class divisions (Savage, 2015). This trend has also inspired publications in the Dutch context (Vrooman et al., 2023). The theoretical underpinnings of most social inequality studies fall within the social stratification tradition, which focuses on individual attributes such as income or obtained education and does not explicitly consider social classes as manifestations of power relations. This situation is similar in many fields of social science research which have to rely on existing data. Relational theories of social inequality based on recognising classes with often conflicting interests help overcome this static view of society by better documenting and analysing dynamic societal structures. Recontextualising inequality research in theories of social class formulated by classic authors such as Weber, Marx and Bourdieu could therefore inspire new, and ultimately more effective, policy approaches addressing stratification, segregation, and societal polarisation. This requires more fine-grained data which our survey purports to collect.

In addition to contributing to the measurement of socioeconomic divisions in society, a more comprehensive picture of social class can also contribute to a better understanding of how people think about societal issues. Class consciousness dictates that people act in accordance with their interests when they identify with their class and understand its position within labour relations (Lukács, 2000). Many people, however, hold contradictory class locations, as many working-class people consider themselves to be middle class and expert workers and managers identify with the bourgeoisie (Franko & Witko, 2023; Wright, 1982). By mapping classes onto class identification, as well as more specifically onto beliefs about inequality, we can bring into focus *why* people hold economic and political ideas that appear to be against their own interests. This will shed light also on related issues such as the decline of labour movement membership, voting behaviour for parties that do not represent class interests or which actively promote class division through anti-immigrant standpoints, and belief in meritocracy as a justification for social inequality in societies with low levels of social mobility.

Our proposed survey would augment the existing rich LISS panel data with a list of detailed questions allowing to construct a class scheme based on the exploitation-based concept of class by American sociologist Erik Olin Wright (1985). Similar data has been collected more recently through the European Social Survey (Leiufrud et al., 2010), which, however, lacks an investigation into wealth, material forms of capital, and questions on class consciousness and inequality beliefs. In addition, most waves of ESS do not include the detailed measurements of economic, cultural and social capital, as well as housing, which can be found in LISS. This makes for a valuable opportunity for new data collection.

3 Research questions

With the following research questions, we aim to use our proposed class scheme in several ways. First, descriptively, by using the generalizable LISS data to describe the Dutch population (RQ1). Second, comparatively, by methodologically validating the class scheme against the backdrop of other existing schemes (RQ2). And third, explanatory, by examining to what extent the class scheme predicts class identification (RQ3) and whether the class scheme and identification with the scheme can explain other social phenomena (RQ4). This led us to the following four research questions that will guide us in using the data to their fullest capacity:

1. What is the nature of socioeconomic divisions in the Netherlands, through the lens of class exploitation?
2. How does stratification based on class exploitation compare to preexisting measures of objective and subjective social class and socioeconomic status?
3. To what extent do people identify with their social class; in other words, what is the level of their class consciousness?
4. What is the explanatory power of stratification based on class exploitation for understanding political attitudes and voting behaviour, and beliefs about inequality, compared to preexisting measures of stratification?

4 Methodological approach

Requested sample size: 2,500 (maximum possible).

Sample composition: People of working age (ages 18-66). This limits the size and costs of the survey, focusing only on respondents most relevant to the focus of this proposal.

Desired timing of the fieldwork: As soon as possible, ideally at the same time as the relevant LISS Core Study questions listed in section 6 (Core Study Work & Schooling, likely April 2024).

Repeated measurements (where applicable): n/a.

Use of existing LISS panel data: See section 6. In case the relevant questions are not available within the same survey date (filled in on the same date), we would like to also ask them in our proposed survey.

5 Implications for research, practice and/or society

With this project we will challenge and extend the current direction of studies on socioeconomic stratification. That is, we argue that current data and methods are insufficient, and our aim is to develop a new tool for the methodological toolkit of stratification research. Of course, studying social class itself does not constitute a new tool. It is, however, a neglected tool which we hope to reinvigorate by reintroducing an exploitation-based class scheme to improve the capabilities of inequality researchers to approach their topic from new angles.

By benchmarking our survey questions to extant and widely used questionnaires (e.g., the European Social Survey and the International Social Survey Programme), our aim is to make maximally comparable our data with existing international datasets. This will enable a direct comparison between current measures of inequality, stratification, and segregation and the class exploitation perspective our data will afford. Specifically, it will allow researchers to compare and contrast societal-level descriptors of inequality, typologies of stratification, and their association with political attitudes and inequality beliefs. By anchoring our survey questions in extant datasets, researchers will be able to readily place the Netherlands in an international perspective. In a next step, we hope to replicate this project in the United States which, we believe, would benefit comparative research and make the LISS module more attractive to use for international researchers.

In sum, the proposed LISS module will shed light on social inequalities and polarization in the Netherlands. A better understanding of the power dynamics within society will allow policy makers to more effectively address the social problems that emerge from these dynamics and work towards more social justice. Our current understanding of social problems is often described in terms of poverty and thus attempted to solve through poverty alleviation. Such solutions usually come after the facts, that is, it does not solve the problem at its core. Policy that is build upon an understanding of the systemic causes (i.e., class dynamics) leading to poverty and inequality is much more likely to solve these problems than just to alleviate them.

6 Preliminary content of the LISS panel survey questions (optional)

Below we list the variables, or more generally question topics which we propose. The same or comparable questions already present in LISS are listed under the variable; all the questions should be asked at the same time point, so we hope our survey could be synchronised with the LISS Core Study Work & Schooling. Another

relevant LISS Core with relevant variables is LISS Economic Situation: Assets; these variables, however, are not equally sensitive to timing.

The listed questions are based on Wright (1985) and Leiufrud et al. (2010).

We would like to gather information on respondents':

- Occupation, isco88
 - o Already in LISS: question cw22o611 (ISCO 08)
- Number of employees
- Ownership of financial assets, agricultural land, livestock, agricultural equipment, non-agricultural enterprises and enterprise assets
 - o See LISS Economic Situation: Assets
- Employment relation
 - o Comparable in LISS: cw22o121, cw22o121
- Responsible for supervising other employees
 - o In LISS: cw22o409
- Number of people responsible for in job
 - o In LISS: cw22o410
- Employment status
 - o Also in LISS, quite detailed
- Allowed to decide how daily work is organised
- Allowed to influence policy decisions about activities of organisation

We would also like to ask class consciousness questions, identifying to what degree the respondent identifies with the reference category of working class (agree/disagree questions); these questions are selected from Wright (1985):

- Corporations benefit owners at the expense of workers and consumers.
- During a strike, management should be prohibited by law from hiring workers to take the place of strikers.
- Big corporations have far too much power in the Dutch society today.
- One of the main reasons for poverty is that the economy is based on private property and profits.
- If given the chance, non-management employees at the place where you work could run things effectively without bosses.
- It is possible for a modern society to run effectively without the profit motive.
- Imagine that workers in a major industry are out on strike over working conditions and wages. Which of the following outcomes would you like to see occur:
 - o (1). the workers win their most important demands;
 - o (2). the workers win some of their demands and make some concessions;
 - o (3). the workers win only a few of their demands and make major concessions;
 - o (4). the workers go back to work without winning any of their demands.

To address our fourth research question, we include a battery of questions gauging respondents' inequality beliefs. All questions are adopted from the International Social Survey Programme 2019 Social Inequality module, which allows for a direct benchmarking of our results with those in over 40 countries across a 35-year period.

Unless otherwise noted, questions are answered on a 5-point Likert scale from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree"

Perceptions of inequality

- Differences in income in the Netherlands are too large
- In all countries, there are differences or even conflicts between different social groups. In your opinion, in the Netherlands how much conflict is there between... ["very strong" to "no conflicts"]
 - o Poor people and rich people?
 - o The working class and the middle class?
 - o Management and workers?

Explanations of inequality

- We have some questions about opportunities for getting ahead. Please tick one box for each of these to show how important you think it is for getting ahead in life...
 - o Having well-educated parents?
 - o Having wealthy parents?
 - o Hard work?
 - o Knowing the right people?
 - o A person's race?
 - o Being born a man or woman?
- How fair or unfair do you think the income distribution is in the Netherlands? ["very fair" to "very unfair"]

Attitudes about inequality

- It is the responsibility of the government to reduce the differences in income between people with high incomes and those with low incomes
- It is the responsibility of private companies to reduce the differences in pay between their employees with high and low pay
- The government should provide a decent standard of living for the unemployed
- Do you feel angry about differences in wealth between the rich and poor?

7 References

- Franko, W. W., & Witko, C. (2023). Unions, class identification, and policy attitudes. *The Journal of Politics*, 85(2), 1-15.
- Leiulfsrud, H., Bison, I., & Solheim, E. (2010). *Social class in Europe II*. Trondheim: NTNU Social Research/Trento University.
- Lukács, G. (2000). *History and class consciousness*. Massachusetts: The MIT Press.
- Piketty, T. (2014). *Capital in the Twenty-First Century*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Savage, M. (2015). *Social class in the 21st century*. London: Penguin UK.
- Vrooman, C., Boelhouwer, J., Iedema, J., & Torre, A. van der. (2023). *Eigentijdse ongelijkheid*. The Hague: The Netherlands Institute for Social Research
- Wright, E. O. (1982). Class boundaries and contradictory class locations, in: Giddens, A. & Held, D. (Eds.), *Classes, power, and conflict: Classical and contemporary debates*. Berkeley: University of California Press, pp. 112-129.
- Wright, E. O. (1985). *Classes*. London: Verso.